

Analysis and Improvement of Service Quality at PT KAI

Using Servqual and IPA Methods

Case Study: Pasar Senen Station- Jakarta

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Abstract. This study aims to determine the effect of station service quality, which includes the dimensions of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, as well as station facilities, on customer satisfaction. The methods used in this study are Service Quality (Servqual) and Importance Performance Analysis (IPA). The results obtained indicate that the service quality values for Tangibles, Reliability, and Responsiveness dimensions fall below customer expectations. The value of service quality for Assurance and Empathy is also below customer expectation. Based on the results of the Cartesian diagram analysis, Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) is identified as a top priority and must be improved in quadrant A. The suggestion for improving service quality is to rearrange and routinely check benches in the waiting room, and officers must enhance their ability to interact directly and communicate with customers. The provision of departure and arrival information through digital media can reduce the use of paper media

Keywords: Service Quality, Servqual, Importance Performance Analysis, IPA, Customer Satisfaction

1 Introduction

Quality service control aims to maintain or surpass the existing level of services provided by the company. This effort is crucial because excellent service quality contributes to customer satisfaction. As customer satisfaction grows, so does loyalty to the company, fostering a harmonious relationship between the company and its customers [1], [11], [12]. Additionally, the significance of word-of-mouth branding cannot be overstated, as it plays a vital role in enhancing the company's communication effectiveness with customers [2] and encouraging repeat purchases of the company's products [3], [13].

Based on PT KAI's customer satisfaction survey in 2022, evidence of dissatisfaction emerged, highlighting concerns related to boarding area facilities, toilets, high platform positions, health service facilities, parking areas, vehicle entry and exit access, and waiting room facilities [4], [14].

Customer satisfaction is a critical aspect that companies must prioritize, achieved through providing quality services. It is the emotional response experienced by customers when comparing the perceived performance of a product to their expectations [5], [15].

The primary aim of this research is to explore the impact of railway station service quality, encompassing dimensions such as tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, as well as station facilities, on customer satisfaction."

2 Literature Review and Methodology

The analysis of customer satisfaction in this study utilizes the Service Quality (Servqual) method and Importance Performance Analysis (IPA). The Servqual method is applied to quantify the gap between customers' perceptions and expectations regarding the quality of the received service. Customer satisfaction is assessed across five dimensions: Tangible, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy [7], [16].

The Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) method is employed to compare customer assessments of the importance level of service quality with the actual performance of service quality. Two methods are used to present IPA data. The first method positions the quadrant intersection lines at the average values on the satisfaction level axis and the priority handling axis, providing insight into the general position of data distribution. The second method situates the quadrant intersection lines at the average values of the observation results on the satisfaction level axis and the priority handling axis, offering a more specific understanding of the position of each factor [8].

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Results

This research involved distributing questionnaires to PT KAI customers at Pasar Senen Station, Jakarta. The questionnaire, utilizing the Likert Scale, was distributed to 100 respondents through Google Forms. The questions in the questionnaire, depicted in Table 1, covered dimensions such as tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

Table 1. Questionnaire

No.	Questions	Customer Perception					Customer Expectation				
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Tangible Dimensions											
1	Do the officers have neat and clean appearances?										
2	Do the stations have strategically placed information boards?										
3	Do the stations have a comfortable and clean waiting room?										
4	Do the stations have a sufficient number of benches?										
Reliability Dimensions											
5	Do the stations provide information on train departures and arrivals?										
6	Do the stations provide ticket cancellation and rescheduling?										
7	Do the stations provide accurate information for ticket purchases?										
8	Do the stations respond to suggestions and feedback from customers?										
9	Do officers serve ticket purchases according to the existing procedures										
Responsiveness Dimensions											
10	Do officers respond to customers when they have problems with the ticket purchase or cancellation procedures?										
11	Do boarding officers serve quick services to customers?										
12	Do officers direct pregnant women according to the existing procedures?										
13	Do officers act proficiently?										
Assurance Dimensions											
14	Do the officer have sufficient knowledge to perform their duties and provide good service?										
15	Do officers show polite and friendly behavior?										
Empathy Dimensions											
16	Is the operational schedule comfortable for all customers?										
17	Do stations always prioritize the interests of customers?										
18	Do officers understand the specific needs of customers?										

3.2 Calculation of Service Quality

In the Servqual method, gap analysis involves two characteristics: a positive gap indicating satisfaction and a negative gap indicating dissatisfaction [9], [17]. In analyzing service quality, the formula (1) is utilized:

$$\text{Service Quality (Q)} = \frac{\text{Perception}}{\text{Expectation}} \quad (1)$$

Table 2. Service Quality Calculation

No	Dimension	Perception	Expectation	Gap	Q = P/E
1	Tangible	4,26	4,56	-0,302	0,934
2	Reliability	4,20	4,58	-0,378	0,918
3	Responsiveness	4,26	4,57	-0,311	0,932
4	Assurance	4,28	4,58	-0,304	0,934
5	Empathy	4,16	4,57	-0,411	0,910
Average		4,229	4,571	-0,341	0,925

From Table 2, the average service quality is 0.925, indicating that the service quality is not yet considered good.

3.4 Importance Performance Analysis (IPA)

After determining the overall gap value, the next step involves the analysis of performance and expectations. This analysis aims to comprehend the position of each attribute in the service to PT KAI customers based on the level of performance/perception and the level of expectations. The perception-expectation quadrant analysis utilizes a Cartesian diagram. In this study, the IPA Cartesian diagram is generated using SPSS 25.

Creating a Cartesian diagram involves dividing the chart into four sections bounded by two intersecting perpendicular lines at points X and Y, where X represents the average of all attribute scores for performance/perception, and Y represents the average of all attribute scores for importance/expectation [10], [18]. The results are depicted in Figure 1."

Fig. 1. Cartesian Diagram

4 Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Conclusion

The conclusions drawn from the results of the service quality analysis, employing the Service Quality method and Importance Performance Analysis at Pasar Senen Station in Jakarta, are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Conclusion of Service Quality

Dimension	Service Quality Score	Max Gap	Attribute
Tangible	0,934	-0,459	Pasar Senen Station has a comfortable and clean waiting area (attribute 3)
Reliability	0,918	-0,500	Pasar Senen Station is genuinely helpful in resolving ticket cancellation and rescheduling issues (attribute 6)
Responsiveness	0,932	-0,357	The staff at Pasar Senen Station responds to customers when they encounter difficulties understanding ticket purchase or cancellation procedures (attribute 6)
Assurance	0,934	-0,324	The staff at Pasar Senen Station has sufficient knowledge to perform their duties and provide good service (attribute 14)
Empathy	0,910	0,469	The operating hours of Pasar Senen Station are convenient for all customers (attribute 16)

Table 4. Conclusion of Importance Performance Analysis

Quadrant	Attribute
A	Pasar Senen Station has a comfortable and clean waiting area Pasar Senen Station has an ample number of benches Pasar Senen Station is genuinely helpful in resolving ticket cancellation and rescheduling issues Pasar Senen Station provides precise and careful services in ticket purchases Pasar Senen responds to suggestions and feedback from customers The staff at Pasar Senen Station responds to customers when they encounter difficulties understanding ticket purchase or cancellation procedures Pasar Senen Station always prioritizes interests

4.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the conducted research, the following recommendations can be made: PT KAI, particularly at Pasar Senen Station, should focus on enhancing service quality attributes in each dimension, especially those identified as top priorities (quadrant A).

References

- [1] Khadka, K., & Maharjan, S.: Customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: Case trivsel städtjänster (trivsel siivouspalvelut), (2017).
- [2] Nikookar, G., Rahrov, E., Razi, S., & Ghassemi, R. A.: Investigating influential factors on word of mouth in service industries: The case of Iran Airline company. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 177, 217–222, (2015).

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- [3] Kitapci, O., Akdogan, C., & Dortyol, I. T.: The impact of service quality dimensions on patient satisfaction, repurchase intentions and word-of-mouth communication in the public healthcare industry. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, (2014). 148, 161–169, (2014).
- [4] ppid.kai.id.: Dokumen Laporan Survey Kepuasan Pelanggan PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) Semester II - Tahun 2022. Retrieved from https://ppid.kai.id/media/konten/111_surveykepuasan2022smster2.pdf, (2022).
- [5] Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L.: *Marketing management 12e*. New Jersey. (2006).
- [6] Radix, I., Indriani, S., & Adriantantri, E.: Kepuasan Nasabah Terhadap Kualitas Pelayanan di Bank BPR Syariah Kota Mojokerto dengan Metode Service Quality (Studi Kasus Tabungan Amanah BANK BPR Syariah Kota Mojokerto). *Jurnal Mahasiswa Teknik Industri*, 3(2), (2020).
- [7] Muhammad, I., Bagus Suardika, & Indriani, S.: Peningkatan Kualitas Pelayanan Dengan Metode Service Quality dan Importance Performance Analysis pada Hero Taman Pinang Indah Sidoarjo. *Jurnal Valtech (Jurnal Mahasiswa Teknik Industri)*, 5(1), 66–72, (2022).
- [8] Jazuli, M., Samanhuji, D., & Handoyo.: Analisis Kualitas Pelayanan Dengan Servqual Dan Importance Performance Analysis Di PT. XYZ. *Juminten: Jurnal Manajemen Industri dan Teknologi*, 01(01), 67–75, (2020).
- [9] Andana, H. G., & Ekawati, Y.: Analisis Kepuasan Pelanggan di Metro Musik Malang Menggunakan Metode SERVQUAL, IPA, dan QFD. *Jurnal Teknik Industri UMC*, 1(1), 22–30. <https://doi.org/10.33479/jtiumc.v1i1.4>, (2021).
- [10] Haris, F., Hadining, A. F., & Sari, R. P.: Analisis Kepuasan Pelanggan ABC Laundry dengan Menggunakan Metode Service Quality, Importance Performance Analysis (IPA), dan Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI), (2020).
- [11] Leninkumar, V.: The Relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Customer Trust on Customer Loyalty. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, Vol. 7, No. 4, (2017).
- [12] Lu, Y., Lu, Y., & Wang, B.: Effects of Dissatisfaction on Customer Repurchase Decisions in E-commerce-An Emotion-Based Perspective. *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, Vol. 13, No. 3:224-237, (2012).
- [13] Musa, M. I., Haeruddin, M. I. W., & Haeruddin, M. I. M.: Customers' repurchase decision in the culinary industry: Do the Big-Five personality types matter?. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research*, 13(1), (2018).
- [14] Cynk, M.: The Influence of Accessibility and Facilities on Tourist Satisfaction to Broken Beach and Angel'S Billabong J. IPTA, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 10–17, 2020, DOI: 10.24843, (2020),
- [15] Li, S.J., Huang, Y.Y. and Yang, M.M. (2011), "How satisfaction modifies the strength of the influence of perceived service quality on behavioral intentions", *Leadership in Health Services*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 91-105.
- [16] Eshghi, A., S. K. Roy and S. Ganguli. (2008). «Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction: An Empirical Investigation in Indian Mobile Telecommunications Services», *Marketing Management Journal*, Vol. 18, No. 2, pp. 119-144
- [17] Chang, Bao-Lin; Kao, Hsiu-O; Lin, Shwu-Jen; Yang, Shu-Hui; Kuo, Yao-Wen; Jerng, Jih-Shuin. 2018. Original Article Quality gaps and priorities for improvement of healthcare service for patients with prolonged mechanical ventilation in the view of family. *Journal of the Formosan Medical Association* (2018) XX, 1- 10.
- [18] Makoe, M., & Nsamba, A. (2019). The gap between student perceptions and expectations of quality support services at the University of South Africa. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 33(2), 132-141.